

Survey "The challenge of the societal impact"

Dear participants,

Thank you for taking the time to participate in our survey titled "The challenge of the social impact: A Swiss-European perspective on organisational legitimacy in university alliances". Your insights are invaluable to us! The purpose of this survey is to understand how university experts view the creation of evidence for societal impact in addressing grand societal challenges. Your feedback will guide us in making informed decisions to enhance our efforts.

The survey will take approximately 15 minutes to complete. Rest assured, all your responses will be anonymised and treated with strict confidentiality. There are no right or wrong answers—what matters most is your honest opinion and experience. The anonymised data will be used for publication.

Your participation is essential in helping us drive societal impact for the benefit of our communities. We sincerely appreciate your support and contribution.

Framing

Universities are seen as important actors for creating societal impact, which is mostly linked to expectations for solutions

Content/topic

From your personal perspective, which content/topics should be given special emphasis at your university to create important societal impact? Please rate the importance of the following topics:

1. Polarisation of societies

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

2. Fight against false information or disinformation

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

3. Advancement of technologies for artificial intelligence

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

4. Fight against islamistic extremism

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

5. Tensions between US and China

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

6. Poverty and social inequality

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

7. Geopolitics of oceans (e.g. resource extraction, trade routes)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

8. Financial/political corruption

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

9. Extreme weather

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

10. Unemployment

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

11. Peace in conflict zones of global interest like Ukraine/Russia or Middle East

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

12. Inflation

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

13. Multipolar world order

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

14. Crime & violence

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

15. Climate change

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

16. Fight against right extremism

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

17. Russia-NATO relations

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

18. Environmental protection in general

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

19. Cost of living

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

20. Protection of liberal democracies

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

21. Digitalisation of societies

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

22. Economic development in your country

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

23. Cyberattacks and other foreign interference

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

24. Geopolitical tensions in the Asia-Pacific region

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

25. Deglobalisation

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

26. Energy security

- Not important
- Slightly important
- Quite important
- Very important
- Not applicable
- Don't know

27. Others, please specify:

28. According to you, is your university already engaging sufficiently in the topics you selected in the list above which you consider important to create societal impact?

- Completely sufficiently
- Sufficiently
- Insufficiently
- Completely insufficiently
- Not applicable
- Don't know

29. Your university is part of the PIONEER-Alliance. Do you think that this membership will change the content focus of your university for creating societal impact?

- Yes
- No
- Not applicable
- Don't know

30. If yes, in what way?

Accountability

From your personal perspective, how important are the following stakeholders for your university when it comes to explaining achievements and performances (accountability) related to creating societal impact?

31. Authorities at the local level (city...)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

32. Authorities at the regional level (e.g. Kanton, Bundesland, region)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

33. Authorities at the national level (e.g. government, accreditation institution, national funding institution)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

34. Private funding institutions

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

35. The local economic stakeholders

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

36. The broader public

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

37. EU funding programmes (e.g. Horizon Europe, Erasmus+...)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

38. Internal stakeholders (e.g. students, staff)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

39. The internal PIONEER project management structure at my university

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

40. The PIONEER Governance Board (Board of Rectors of alliance member institutions)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

41. Others, please specify:

Instruments

How important are the following instruments regarding their usefulness as tools for measuring your university's performance related to creating societal impact?

The list of items is split into two groups: a) Group of instruments which are linked to policy agendas; and b) Group of instruments which cover the international outreach and spread, thus expected greater impact

a) Group of instruments which are linked to policy agendas.

42. The national quality assurance agency (e.g. OAQ Organe für Akkreditierung und Qualitätssicherung der Schweizerischen Hochschulen)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

43. Internal evaluation (e.g. teaching evaluation)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

44. Performance-based funding (e.g. Swiss National Research Foundation)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

45. Performance-based pay

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

46. Thematic funding (e.g. PIONEER-specific funding, "Themenfelder" (BFH), ...)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

Instruments

How important are the following instruments regarding their usefulness as tools for measuring your university's performance related to creating societal impact?

b) Group of instruments which cover the international outreach and spread, thus expected greater impact.

47. International rankings

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

48. Quantity of EU-funding

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

49. Degree student enrolment rates

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

50. Enrolment rates of European degree students

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

51. Enrolment rates of international (non-European) degree students

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

52. Share of international/European student mobility

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

53. Share of international/European staff mobility

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

54. Size of your university's European network

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

55. Size of your university's international network

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

56. Total number of projects with European partners at your university

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

57. Total number of projects with international partners at your university

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

Legitimacy 1

How important are the following stakeholders when it comes to providing implicit guiding principles (e.g. policy agendas, business models, expectations from politics or the population) for what you do at your university and/or exerting pressure for appropriate conduct of your university related to creating societal impact:

58. European Commission

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

59. National Funding Agencies

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

60. International funding agencies

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

61. Student organisation

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

62. Staff organisation

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

63. The public/the society (e.g. through social media)

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

64. Business partners

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

65. Non-governmental organisations

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

66. Political parties

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

67. Authorities at the local level

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

68. University alliance partners

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

69. Other project partners

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

70. Journalists

Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

71. Others, please specify:

Legitimacy 2

To what extent does the following statement apply to you? Please rate the statements on a scale from 'don't agree at all' to 'fully agree'.

72. "My university plays/must play a role as an agent for digital and green transition."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

73. "If we are to increase the efficiency of creating societal impact, we need more European partnerships."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

74. "If we are to increase the efficiency of creating impact for society, we need more non-European partnerships."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

75. "We can increase the impact for society in what we are doing by strengthening the collaboration with our local ecosystem."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

76. "European values are not important to my university's efforts for creating societal impact."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

77. "Solutions for creating societal impact need the implication of many different actors."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

78. "Many researchers at my university are caught in their silos, which is counterproductive to creating societal impact."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

79. "Selling an idea to the wider public needs the inclusion of perspectives of different fields or areas of expertise."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

80. "My university supports interdisciplinary research with specific incentives"

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

81. "The PIONEER alliance will help significantly increase the societal impact of my university."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

82. "The PIONEER alliance will create significantly better opportunities for our stakeholders to increase their societal impact than without the alliance."

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

83. "Only a European network of stakeholder ecosystems can create significant societal impact in the future".

I don't agree at all	I mostly don't agree	I mostly agree	I fully agree	Not applicable	Don't know
<input type="radio"/>					

Section 7

84. How important are the following values for your university (for achieving the university's goals, not you personally)?

	Not important	Slightly important	Quite important	Very important	Not applicable	Don't know
Human dignity	<input type="radio"/>					
Freedom	<input type="radio"/>					
Democracy	<input type="radio"/>					
Equality	<input type="radio"/>					
Rule of law	<input type="radio"/>					
Human rights	<input type="radio"/>					

Final question

85. From your personal point of view, list the three most important elements which enable your university to create societal impact.

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